

trans-Dihalo-tetrakis Complexes of Rhodium(III) with some Imidazole Derivatives

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The complexes of imidazole, benzimidazole and substituted benzimidazoles with some platinum metal ions have been reported in early communications^{1,2}. Growing physiological and anticancer activity of Pt-metal complexes tempted us to pursue studies on Pt-metal complexes with some physiologically active imidazole derivatives. Here we report preparation and characterisation of diacido-complexes of rhodium(III) with imidazole (IzH), *N*-methylimidazole (NMIzH) and 2-methylimidazole (2MIzH).

Results and Discussion

The dihalotetrakis complexes of Rh^{III} are obtained as halide [RhL₄X₂]X (X = Cl, Br or I) and perchlorate salt [RhL₄Cl₂]ClO₄·H₂O. The electrical conductance values (Table 1) of all the complexes reveal that they are

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd./ (Colour)	Metal% : Found/ (Calcd.)	Elec. cond. Ω ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ cm ²
[Rh(IzH) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl (Yellow)	21.45 (21.37)	Aq 128, 144 ^a
[Rh(IzH) ₄ Cl ₂]ClO ₄ (Yellow)	18.68 (18.86)	Aq 115, 131 ^a
[Rh(IzH) ₄ Br ₂]Br (Yellow)	16.92 (16.73)	Aq 108, 135 ^a
[Rh(IzH) ₄ I ₂]I (Brown)	13.48 (13.61)	E 78
[Rh(2MIzH) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl·H ₂ O (Yellow)	18.30 (18.52)	Aq 115, 140 ^a
[Rh(2MIzH) ₄ Cl ₂]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O (Yellow)		Aq 112
[Rh(2MIzH) ₄ Br ₂]Br (Yellow)	15.52 (15.31)	Aq 98, 125 ^a
[Rh(2MIzH) ₄ I ₂]I (Brown)	12.86 (12.67)	
[Rh(NMIzH) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl (Yellow)	19.00 (19.14)	Aq 113, 135 ^a
[Rh(NMIzH) ₄ Cl ₂]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O (Yellow)		Aq 111
[Rh(NMIzH) ₄ Br ₂]Br (Yellow)	15.61 (15.31)	Aq 115, 142 ^a
[Rh(NMIzH) ₄ I ₂]I (Brown)	12.77 (12.67)	E 86

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and halogen analyses. ^aAt room temperature after 2 h. Aq = aqueous solution, E = ethanolic solution.

1 : 1 electrolytes^{3,4}. The electrical conductance values of the aqueous solutions increase slowly at room temperature, which is attributed to aquation. The hydrated complexes on heating lose water molecule below 100° indicating that H₂O is not coordinated to the metal atom. The complexes are diamagnetic which supports the oxidation state of +3 for rhodium in these complexes.

The electronic spectra of the rhodium(III) complexes in water or ethanol (Table 2) display two distinct bands or one band and second shoulder in the region 300–500 nm. Rhodium(III) displays two spin-allowed transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} as well as two spin-forbidden

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (nm) OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} (ε _{max})	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g} (ε _{max})
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(en) ₂ Cl ₂] ⁺	286	(130) 406 (75)*
<i>cis</i> -[Rh(en) ₂ Cl ₂] ⁺	293	(200) 352 (250)*
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(en) ₂ Br ₂] ⁺	276	(1800) 425 (100)*
<i>cis</i> -[Rh(en) ₂ Br ₂] ⁺	276 sh	(900) 326 (210)*
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(py) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl	—	— 409 (100)*
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(py) ₄ Br ₂]Br	—	— 439 (118)*
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(py) ₄ I ₂]I	401	(9100) 485 (600)*
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(IzH) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl	294 sh	408 (68)
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(IzH) ₄ Cl ₂]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O	294, 270 sh	408 (69)
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(IzH) ₄ Br ₂]Br	286 sh	438 (82)
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(IzH) ₄ I ₂]I	404	470 sh —
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(2MIzH) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl	270, 255 sh	432 (91)
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(2MIzH) ₄ Br ₂]Br	—	448 (112)
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(2MIzH) ₄ I ₂]I	404, 310, 270 sh	510 sh —
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(NMIzH) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl	—	410 (71)
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(NMIzH) ₄ Br ₂]Br	—	442 (126)
<i>trans</i> -[Rh(NMIzH) ₄ I ₂]I	400	(7800) 468 sh —

*From Ref. 3.

weak bands due to singlet-triplet transitions ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{2g} in octahedral field^{3,4}. The spin-allowed transitions are quite sensitive to the configuration of the complexes³. The *trans*-complexes exhibit ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transition of low ε_{max} value at lower energy than those of the corresponding *cis*-complexes (Table 1)^{3,4}. If only one form is isolated then the stereochemistry is suggested from the value of the molar extinction coefficient at maxima^{3,4}.

The ethanolic solution of the dihalo complexes [RhL₄X₂]⁺ (L = IzH, 2MIzH or NMIzH; X = Cl, Br or I)

display a spin-allowed transition ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ in the visible region. The ϵ_{\max} values of the dichloro and the dibromo complexes lie in the range 68–126 similar to *trans*-tetrakis complexes $[\text{RhB}_4\text{X}_2]^+$ (B = py, alkyl pyrimidine, thiazole etc.). The second spin-allowed band ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ is observed as shoulder or enveloped in C-T transitions.

The coordination of imidazole and *N*- or 2-substituted imidazole with metal atoms has been well established through tertiary nitrogen of imidazole ring from the X-ray studies of $[\text{Zn}(\text{IzH})_4\text{Cl}_2]^{5+}$ as well as proton-nmr and ir spectra of a number of transition metal complexes of imidazole and substituted imidazoles⁶. The lowering of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ stretching vibrations of ligands (1 620–1 650 cm^{-1}) to lower frequencies in the present complexes also supports the bonding of imidazole and NMIzH and 2MIzH with tertiary nitrogen atom. The complex perchlorates $[\text{RhL}_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ display a strong broad band at 1 105 cm^{-1} attributed to ionic perchlorate group. In far-ir region, the dichloro complexes $[\text{RhL}_4\text{Cl}_2]^+$ displaying a medium band at 310 \pm 15 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{Rh}-\text{Cl}}$ vibration. The absence of splitting in $\nu_{\text{Rh}-\text{Cl}}$ suggests *trans*-coordination. A medium band observed at 250–255 cm^{-1} is tentatively assigned to (Rh–N) stretch similar to other heterocyclic base (M–N) stretches⁷.

Experimental

The ligands, imidazole, *N*-methylimidazole and 2-methylimidazole (Fluka) were used as such.

$[\text{RhL}_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (L = IzH, 2MIzH or NMIzH; n = 0 or 1) : An ethanolic solution of hydrated rhodium(III) chloride (1.0 g in 50 ml) was refluxed with an excess of the appropriate ligand (about 1 : 4.5 molar ratio) on a steam-bath for ~1 h during which the rose-red colour of rhodium(III) chloride was changed to light yellow. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 3–4 by adding a few drops of dilute HCl and then concentrated to a small volume (10–15 ml) and cooled, when a cream yellow crystalline precipitate of the complexes separated. The products were filtered, washed with a few drops of cold ethanol and dried in air.

$[\text{RhL}_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (L = IzH, 2MIzH or NMIzH; n = 0 or 1) : The filtrate obtained after collecting the above

dichloro complexes was treated with an aqueous solution of NaClO_4 (2 g in 5 ml) and cooled in freeze overnight when the complex perchlorates separated out as a cream-yellow crystalline precipitate. The products were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in air.

$[\text{RhL}_4\text{X}_2]_x \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (L = IzH, 2MIzH or NMIzH; X = Br or I; n = 0 or 1) : An aqueous solution of the dichloro complexes $[\text{RhL}_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (0.5 g in 20–30 ml) was refluxed with 4–5 fold excess of an aqueous solution of appropriate sodium or potassium halide (20–25 ml; 10%) on a steam-bath for ~2 h. The dihalo complexes separated out slowly from the refluxate either in hot or on concentrating and cooling them overnight to ice-temperature. The products were washed with cold water and ethanol and dried in air.

The electrical conductance, magnetic susceptibility and absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded as reported earlier². The ir spectra (KBr/nujol) of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

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